

The Influence of Students Motivation and Learning Readiness on Students Learning Outcomes in IPS Subjects Grade IX SMP Negeri 2 Siantar

Koko Okto Rizki Sianipar^{1*}, Injen Pardamean Butar-Butar², Sotarduga Sihombing³
Universitas HKBP Nommensen Pematang Siantar, Indonesia

Corresponding Author: Koko Oct Rizki Sianipar; kokosianipar01@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

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This research aims to determine the influence of Learning Motivation and Readiness to learn on student learning outcomes in social studies subjects in class IX SMP NEGERI 2 SIANTAR. The variables in this research are learning motivation and readiness to learn as independent variables and learning outcomes as the dependent variable. This type of research is quantitative research with a quantitative descriptive approach, with a research population of class IX students at SMP NEGERI 2 SIANTAR and a research sample of class IX students at SMP NEGERI 2 SIANTAR consisting of 155 students selected using Simple Random *Sampling* . Data collection techniques use instruments: (1) Learning Motivation questionnaire, (2) Learning Readiness questionnaire, and (3) Learning Outcomes questionnaire. The results of this research show that: (1) there is a positive and significant influence of learning motivation on learning outcomes, this result can be seen in the t test where the calculated t value of Learning Motivation (2.051) > t table value (1.65474) which means that this variable significant. (2) there is a positive and significant influence of learning readiness on learning outcomes (1.903) > t table value (1.65474) which means this variable is significant. (3) Learning Motivation and Learning Readiness together influence learning outcomes, these results can be seen in the F test where the calculated F value (14.348) is > compared to the F table value (2.66). The R *Square* coefficient of determination test was found to be 0.159, meaning that 15.9% of the Learning Motivation and Learning Readiness variables had an influence on student learning outcomes at the SIANTAR NEGERI 2 SMP school and the remaining 84.1% was the influence of other variables not examined in this research.

INTRODUCTION

Motivation to learn can develop activities and initiatives that can direct and maintain persistence in carrying out learning activities. In line with this, there are several indicators to identify students who are motivated in learning, including:

1. There is passion and desire to succeed.
2. There is encouragement and need for learning.
3. Have a high level of curiosity or curiosity
4. Have self-confidence
5. Have high concentration power in studying.
6. Difficulties are considered challenges that must be overcome
7. Have high patience and fighting power.

Student learning readiness is an important factor that every student must have in carrying out learning, remembering that learning activities will be successful if a student has high learning readiness, both regarding knowledge, basic drawing skills, and learning equipment that a student must have. Therefore, a teacher must pay attention to the readiness of his students in carrying out learning activities every day.

The indicators to determine whether a student has Readiness to Learn include:

1. Condition Physical, Mental and Emotional
2. Skills, knowledge and other understanding that have been learned.

So that the absence of learning motivation within a student will influence the learning outcomes that will be achieved later. Where a student will be lazy to do something, not active in the ongoing learning process. And the lack of students' learning readiness in class will also cause students to become less enthusiastic about participating in learning, and not dare to ask questions during learning and when the teacher asks questions students do not dare to answer the questions. So from the problems above, the factors that are thought to influence the learning outcomes of class IX students focus on Learning Motivation and Learning Readiness. If these factors are not ignored, it will affect the learning outcomes of each student at school.

Based on the description of the problem above, it is clear that student learning motivation in social studies subjects and student learning readiness in social studies subjects are the dominant factors in determining students' success in carrying out their learning activities, to achieve good learning outcomes. So the researcher was interested in conducting research with the title " The Influence of Students Motivation and Learning Readiness on Students Learning Outcomes in IPS Subjects Grade IX SMP Negeri 2 Siantar "

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

1. Motivation Study Student

Istarani & Intan Pulungan (2016:5-6) " Motivation is Encouragement someone appears _ from in nor from outside yourself can _ influence desire Study someone and something conscious effort _ For moving , directing and guarding Act in demand someone to order him encouraged For Act do so that reach results or objective certain "

Furthermore Khodijah (2014:150-151) explains definition Motivation Study as something driving force that changes energy in self somebody to in form activity real

For reach objective certain . In other words, motivation is a psychological condition that encourages someone to do something

2. Learning Readiness

Slameto (2010; 59) stated that readiness is "preparedness to respond or React" which means Readiness is preparation For give response or react . This means that readiness needs to be considered in the learning process because when students are ready to learn, their learning outcomes will be better. Readiness is needed in the teaching and learning process because when students are ready, it will be easier for them to participate in learning.

3. Learning Outcomes

Wina Sanjaya (2007;63) said Activity learning that is built by teachers and students is successful activities . _ As successful activity , then _ all something that teachers and students do should directed For reach results have been determined . Thus, in a learning setting, results are the binding force for all teacher and student activities. Therefore, formulating results is the first step that must be taken in designing a learning program.

METHODS

In this research, field research was carried out using quantitative research, as stated by Sugiono (2018; 17) quantitative research can be interpreted as research based on the philosophy of positivism, used to research certain populations and samples, data collection using research instruments, data analysis quantitative/statistical in nature, with the aim of testing predetermined hypotheses.

Based on the researcher's title "The Influence of Learning Motivation and Learning Readiness on the Economics Learning Outcomes of Class IX Students at SMP NEGERI 2 SIANTAR. So the research location and time of the research was carried out at SMP NEGERI 2 SIANTAR. This research was carried out at SMP NEGERI 2 SIANTAR in October 2023 until completion. The population in this study were all class IX students of SMP NEGERI 2 SIANTAR, totaling 251 students. The sample in this study was 155 students .

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Instrument Validity and Reliability Test Results

After testing the instrument, the researcher then tabulated the results of the respondents' answers by arranging answer codes according to the classification of answers in table form. Tabulation of respondents' answers was carried out with the help of the *Microsoft Excel program* and using analytical data using analytical data in the *SPSS 21 program* . From the results of the calculations carried out you can determine whether or not the statement items in the research instrument are valid.

The statement item is declared valid if the $r_{\text{calculated}} \geq r_{\text{table}}$ with a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$. From the results of the validity test, it can be seen that the correlation between each question item and the total score of $n = 30$ shows that the r_{table} is 0.361. This means that if the correlation value is more than 0.361 then the question is considered valid. The statement items that will be used when testing the hypothesis are only valid statement items, while invalid items cannot be used in research.

The instrument reliability test is carried out if all research instruments have been tested for validity. The instrument reliability test is carried out to determine the level of confidence in the research instrument used as a tool for collecting data. To calculate the reliability test of the research instrument, the Cronbach alpha formula is used . The instrument is declared reliable if the Cronbach Alpha coefficient > 0.6 .

Instrument Validity Test

Calculation of the Validity of the Motivation to learn questionnaire consists of 21 statement items, the Readiness to learn questionnaire consists of 19 statement items, and learning outcomes are obtained from the results of the mid-semester exam which is carried out by automatic calculation with SPSS 21 program analysis data. After testing and analyzing *with* statistics .

Items that are declared valid are items that have a correlation value $(r) > 0.361$, while items that have a correlation value $(r) > 0.361$ are valid questionnaire items. This can be concluded that for Motivation to learn (X_1) it is known that there are 21 items in the questionnaire which have a correlation value $(r) > 0.361$, there are 21 valid questionnaire items, for the Readiness to learn questionnaire (X_2) it is known that there are 19 items in the questionnaire. which has a correlation value $(r) > 0.361$ for 19 valid questionnaire items or all valid questionnaires, and for learning outcomes (Y) obtained from the results of the student's mid-semester exam. So the questionnaire used in this research is a valid statement. Where in this research 40 questionnaire items were used in this research.

Instrument Reliability Test

For the questionnaire reliability criteria, if $r_{count} > r_{table}$ with a significant level ($\alpha = 0.05$) then the questionnaire is said to be reliable. However, if $r_{count} \leq r_{table}$ then the questionnaire is considered to have no reliability. If the *Cronbach Alpha value* is > 0.60 it is said to be reliable, but if the *Cronbach Alpha value* is < 0.60 it is said to be unreliable.

Cronbach Alpha > 0.60 is declared reliable, and if the *Cronbach Alpha value* is < 0.60 then it is declared unreliable. From the data obtained, it is known that *the Cronbach Alpha* obtained was $0.924 > 0.60$. From the results of the reliability calculation for Learning Motivation, it can be concluded that the research instrument (X1) in the research questionnaire used is reliable. If the *Cronbach Alpha value* is > 0.60 then it is declared reliable, and if the *Cronbach Alpha value* is < 0.60 then it is declared unreliable. From the data obtained, it is known that *the Cronbach Alpha* obtained was $0.944 > 0.60$. From the results of the reliability calculation for Learning Readiness, it can be concluded that the research instrument (X2) in the research questionnaire used is reliable.

Data Normality Test

Figure 1. Normal Probability P-Plot Curve

Based on Figure 1 Test results p-plot graph shows that the data spreads around the diagonal line and follows diagonal direction that states that the data meets assumption normality and data stated normally distributed . This can be seen in figure 1 above.

Multicollinearity Test

Table 4.1 Multicollinearity Test Results

Coefficients ^a			
Model		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
1	Motivation Study	,471	2,125
	Readiness Study	,471	2,125
a. Dependent Variable: Learning Outcomes			

Assumption from *Tolerance* and *Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)* can stated that if $VIF > 10$ and *Tolerance* value < 0.10 then happen multicollinearity , and if $VIF < 10$ and *Tolerance* value > 0.10 then No happen multicollinearity . Based on table 1 is known that variable VIF value discipline learning and environment Study is $1,837 < 10$ and value *Tolerance* value $0.471 > 0.10$ then can concluded that data _ No happen multicollinearity

Heteroscedasticity Test

Figure 2 Scatterplot curve

Based on Figure 2, it can be seen that the points are spread above and below the number 0 on the Y axis. Thus it can be concluded that heteroscedasticity does not occur.

Multiple Regression Analysis Test

The purpose of the multiple regression analysis test is to determine the direction and how much influence the independent variable has on the dependent variable.

Table 4.2 Multiple Regression Analysis Test Results

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	84,085	,673		125,020	,000
	Motivation to learn	-.023	.011	-.222	2,051	,042
	Readiness to Learn	-.021	.11	-.206	1,903	,059

a. Dependent Variable: Learning Outcomes

Next, the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable is tested with a confidence interval of 95% or $\alpha = 5\%$.

The constant value (a) in table 4.10 is known to be 84,085 while the value of Learning Motivation (b1) is -.023 and the value of Readiness to learn (b2) is -.21, so the regression equation is:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + e$$

$$Y = 84.085 + -.023X_1 + -.21X_2 +.673$$

1. A constant of 84.085 means that the consistent value of the learning outcome variable is 84.085.
2. The regression coefficient X1 is -.023 and X2 is -.021. The regression coefficient is positive, so it can be said that the direction of influence of variable X1 and variable X2 on Y is positive.

t test

Partial test (t) was used For know is hypothesis used _ accepted or rejected , with remember 95% confidence or $\alpha=5\%$, with condition as following :

1. If $t_{\text{count}} > t_{\text{table}}$, then the independent variable has an effect on the dependent variable.
2. If $t_{\text{count}} < t_{\text{table}}$, then the independent variable has no effect on the dependent variable.

Table 4.3 t test results

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	84,085	,673		125,020	,000
	Motivation to learn	-.023	.011	-.222	2,051	,042
	Readiness to Learn	-.021	.11	-.206	1,903	,059

a. Dependent Variable: Learning Outcomes

calculated t value of Learning Motivation (2.051) is greater than the t_{table} (1.65474) and the calculated t value of Learning Readiness (1.903) is greater than the t_{table} (1.65474). Thus, it is known that the independent variable has a significant effect on the dependent variable.

F test

The F test is carried out to find out whether the independent variables together have an influence on the dependent variable. In this case, the $t_{\text{calculated}}$ F is compared with the F_{table} with the following conditions:

1. If $F_{\text{count}} > F_{\text{table}}$, then H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted
2. If $F_{\text{count}} < F_{\text{table}}$, then H_1 is rejected and H_0 is rejected.

Table 4.4 F Test Results

ANOVA ^a					
Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.

1	Regression	316.133	2	9,065	14,348	,000 ^b
	Residual	1149.553	152	,632		
	Total	114,160	154			
a. Dependent Variable: Learning Outcomes						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Learning Motivation, Learning Readiness						

Based on table 4.4. It was found that the *calculated* F value (14,348) was greater than the *table* F value (2.66). This indicates that the research results reject Ho and accept H1. Thus, simultaneously learning motivation and students' learning readiness influence the student learning outcome variables at SMP NEGERI 2 SIANTAR school with a significant level of influence. This gives meaning to the hypothesis which states that students' learning motivation and learning readiness simultaneously influence student learning outcome variables at SMP NEGERI 2 SIANTAR school as acceptable.

Coefficient of Determination Test

**Table 4.5 Coefficient of Determination Test Results
Model Summary^b**

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,399 ^a	,159	,148	,795

a. Predictors: (Constant), readiness to learn , motivation to learn

b. Dependent Variable: Learning Outcomes

The *R Square coefficient of determination value* in table 4.5 is known to be 0.159. Which means that 15.9% of the Learning Motivation and Learning Readiness variables influence student learning outcomes at the SIANTAR NEGERI 2 SMP school. Meanwhile, 84.1% is the influence of other variables not examined in this research.

Discussion

Research was conducted to determine the influence of learning motivation and learning readiness on social studies learning outcomes for class IX students at SMP NEGERI 2 SIANTAR. In this research there are 3 problem formulations that need to be answered through the research that has been carried out.

1. The Influence of Learning Motivation on Social Studies Learning Results for Class IX SMP NEGERI 2 SIANTAR

Based on the results of the research that has been carried out, the regression coefficient value is 2.051, the *t* _{table} is 1.6 5474 . So, it is obtained that *t* _{count} > *t* _{table} , namely 2.051 > 1.6 5474 . So it can be seen that the learning motivation variable (X1) rejects the null hypothesis (Ho1) and accepts the alternative hypothesis (Ha1). Which means there is a positive and significant influence between the learning discipline variables on the social studies learning outcomes for class IX SMP NEGERI 2 SIANTAR. The regression coefficient value obtained from this research is -.023, this shows that with every additional 1 score point for the Parental Attention variable , there will be an increase in learning outcomes of -.023. On the other hand, if the

learning interest score decreases by 1 point, this will be followed by a decrease in learning outcomes of 0.599.

2. The Influence of Learning Readiness on Social Sciences learning outcomes for Class IX SMP NEGERI 2 SIANTAR

Based on the results of the research that has been carried out, the regression coefficient value of 0.159 is obtained. The $t_{\text{calculated}}$ value of learning motivation (1.903) is greater than the t_{table} (1.65474), so it can be seen that the Learning Readiness variable (X2) rejects the null hypothesis (Ho2) and accept the alternative hypothesis (Ha2). Thus it can be concluded that the independent variable has a significant effect on the dependent variable. Which means there is a positive and significant influence between the Learning Readiness variable on the Social Sciences Learning Outcomes for Class IX SMP NEGERI 2 SIANTAR. The regression coefficient value obtained from this research is 0.159, this shows that with every addition of 1 score point for the Learning Readiness variable, there will be an increase in Learning Outcomes of 0.159. On the other hand, if the Learning Motivation score decreases by 1 point, this will be followed by a decrease in learning outcomes of 0.159.

3. The Influence of Learning Motivation and Learning Readiness on Social Studies Learning Outcomes of Class IX Students at SMP NEGERI 2 SIANTAR

To answer the third problem formulation, the influence of Learning Motivation and Learning Readiness on Class IX Social Sciences learning outcomes can be seen from the results of research that has been carried out as follows:

The independent variables, namely Learning Motivation and Learning Readiness, simultaneously influence student learning outcomes. This is in accordance with the results of the hypothesis test carried out with the help of SPSS release 21. It was found that the $F_{\text{calculated}}$ value (14.348) was greater than the F_{table} value (2.66). This indicates that the research results reject the null hypothesis (Ho3) and accept the alternative hypothesis (Ha3). Thus, together, learning motivation and students' learning readiness influence the learning outcome variables of Class IX SMP NEGERI 2 SIANTAR students. with a significant level of influence. This gives meaning to the hypothesis which states that students' learning motivation and learning readiness jointly influence student learning outcome variables at SMP NEGERI 2 SIANTAR school as acceptable.

Research conducted by Dyah Ayu Puspitaningrum (2018) students from Yogyakarta State University entitled " " *The Influence of Learning Motivation and Learning Readiness on Student Learning Outcomes in History Subjects Classes* The research results show:

1. There is a positive influence of learning motivation on economic learning outcomes with a t value of 9.984 and a significance value of 0.000.
2. There is a positive influence on students' learning readiness on economic learning outcomes with a t value of 4.487 and a significance value of 0.000.
3. There is a positive influence of learning motivation and students' learning readiness together on economic learning outcomes with an F value of 180.033 and a significance value of 0.000. The amount of R^2 is 79.3% while the remaining 20.7% is explained by other variables not studied.

"The place/object of research carried out by the previous researcher and the author's research place are different, but the problem identification at school is the same." Therefore, to be able to improve learning outcomes, it is necessary to increase

learning motivation in learning by increasing according to indicators. Apart from that, readiness to learn also influences students in learning because the enthusiasm and desire to learn comes from a student, so teachers are asked to help students to be enthusiastic in the learning process and produce good learning results.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

There are several conclusions made by researchers based on the research results that have been researched and discussed in the previous chapter, namely as follows:

1. There is a positive and significant influence of Learning Motivation on learning outcomes. This result can be seen in the t test where the $t_{\text{calculated}}$ value of Learning Readiness (2.051) > t_{table} value (1.65474) which means this variable is significant.
2. There is a positive and significant influence of Learning Readiness on Learning Outcomes, this result can be seen in the t test where the $t_{\text{calculated}}$ value of learning independence (1.903) > t_{table} value (1.65474) which means this variable is significant.
3. Learning Motivation and Learning Readiness together influence learning outcomes, this result can be seen in the F test where the $F_{\text{calculated}}$ value (14,348) > F_{table} value (2.66). The R Square coefficient of determination test was found to be 0.159, which means that 15.9% of the Learning Motivation and Learning Readiness variables influence student learning outcomes at the SIANTAR NEGERI 2 SMP school, and the remaining 84.1% is the influence of variables not examined in this research.

FURTHER STUDY

It is recommended that other researchers who will research the same problems be able to choose research subjects with different characteristics and be able to research other variables that can influence economic learning outcomes besides the variables of learning discipline and learning independence, so that they can further develop knowledge.

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